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Performance Appraisal And Employee Job Performance Of Non-Academic Staff In Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of performance appraisal on the job performance of non-academic staff at Delta State University, Abraka. The specific objectives were to determine the influence of supervisor evaluation, 360-degree feedback, and the rating scale method on employee performance. The study adopted a survey research design to examine the relationship between the variables under investigation. The population comprised 1,767 non-academic staff, from which a sample of 353 respondents was drawn using Taro Yamane's formula and Bowley's proportionate sampling technique. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analysis. Findings revealed that supervisor evaluation ($T=2.216$, $p<0.05$), 360-degree feedback ($T=2.065$, $p<0.05$), and the rating scale method ($T=5.230$, $p<0.05$) each exerted a significant positive effect on job performance. These results underscore the relevance of structured appraisal systems in improving staff efficiency and overall institutional productivity. Based on the findings, the study recommends that universities, particularly Delta State University, adopt comprehensive performance appraisal frameworks integrating supervisor evaluation, regular multi-source feedback, and effective rating scales. Furthermore, training should be provided for staff involved in appraisal processes to enhance the accuracy and quality of feedback. Equipping supervisors with appropriate evaluative skills is essential to improving employee performance outcomes. Finally, periodic reviews of appraisal practices are encouraged to ensure their alignment with institutional objectives and evolving workforce needs. By strengthening appraisal systems, higher institutions can foster enhanced job performance among non-academic staff and promote organizational effectiveness.

Keywords: Performance Appraisal, Supervisor Evaluation, 360-Degree Feedback, Rating Scale, Employee Job Performance

INTRODUCTION

An organization's ability to succeed relies on the caliber and traits of its workforce. Without personnel, organizational goals and objectives cannot be achieved. Employees must be inspired to work in the organization's best interests of the organization. According to Ijeuru, Odonye, and Wuyep (2024), in a highly competitive environment, organization itself cannot produce the results that many stakeholders within the organization anticipate without the assistance of its most precious asset—its people. Research shows that employees who feel inadequately assessed are less likely to fully engage with their responsibilities, which can reduce overall productivity and organizational effectiveness (Dasanayaka et

al., 2021). Additionally, the lack of constructive feedback often leaves employees uncertain about their strengths and areas needing improvement, which can impede their professional growth (Nutakor, 2022). Therefore, there is a need to assess employee performance so as to create a more productive and supportive work environment within the university

Since employee performance affects organizational performance, an organization must continuously assess the abilities and competencies of its workforce in order to attain higher performance (Ijeuru, et al., 2024). This assessment procedure is called performance appraisal. According to Dike, Anetoh, Eboh, and Obiorah (2021), performance appraisal is regarded as one of the most widely used management tools due to its administrative uses in the areas of bonuses, promotions, and salaries. These are used for employee evaluation in order to achieve organizational planning and motivational goals. Without a doubt, the human resource management unit's consistent effort in conducting assessment of performance is crucial to determining the strengths and shortcomings of their staff. Employers or management can use it to increase the organization's competitiveness, commitment, productivity, and profitability (Dike, et al., 2021).

Performance appraisal systems (PAS) play a crucial role in higher education institutions by assessing and enhancing employee performance. These systems serve multiple purposes, including identifying strengths and weaknesses, fostering professional development, and aligning individual goals with the institution's objectives (Osman, Kyeraa & Opoku, 2024). In universities, effective performance appraisal is essential not only for academic staff but also for non-academic employees who are vital to administrative and support functions. The influence of PAS extends beyond mere evaluation; it impacts job satisfaction, performance, organizational loyalty, and the overall quality of education (Balu, 2022). However, many institutions face difficulties in implementing effective appraisal systems due to biases, a lack of standardized criteria, and insufficient training for evaluators (Balu, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

The performance appraisal process is a crucial element of human resource management in educational institutions, especially within universities. However, there are notable gaps in current performance appraisal practices that impact the job performance of non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria. .

The effectiveness of universities largely hinges on how efficiently both academic and non-academic staff delivers essential services that support the institution's goals. However, there are growing concerns regarding the inadequate job performance of non-academic staff within these universities. Issues such as administrative inefficiencies, delays in service delivery, and a lack of commitment among non-academic personnel have adversely affected the smooth operation of universities. Feedback from students and personal observations have highlighted problems like slow processing of academic records, poor facility maintenance, and inefficiencies in administrative tasks, all of which led to frustration and diminished institutional effectiveness.

University management across various institutions in Delta State has also voiced concerns about laxity, absenteeism, and poor responsiveness among non-academic staff, which significantly obstructs organizational productivity. Despite these challenges, the potential of performance appraisal as a means to enhance job performance has not been thoroughly explored. A well-designed appraisal system could act as a valuable tool for boosting employee motivation, accountability, and overall efficiency.

Although, several studies have been carried out on the link between performance appraisal and employee job performance. However, relatively few studies have been conducted on the relationship between performance appraisal and employee job performance of non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria. Therefore, addressing these gaps is vital not only for improving individual employee performance but also for creating a more productive and supportive work environment within universities.

Objectives of the Study

The principal objective of the study is to investigate the relationship between performance appraisal and employee job performance. The specific objectives are:

1. To examine the effect of supervisor evaluation method of performance appraisal on job performance among non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka.
2. To establish the impact of 360-Degree feedback method of performance appraisal on job performance among non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka.
3. To investigate the influence of rating scale method of performance appraisal on job performance among non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka.

Research Questions

Flowing from the statement of problem, the following research questions were raised.

1. To what extent does supervisor evaluation method of performance appraisal affects job performance among non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka?
2. To what extent does 360-Degree feedback method of performance appraisal impacts job performance among non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka?
3. To what extent does rating scale method of performance appraisal influences job performance among non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka?

Research Hypotheses

The research hypotheses are stated in the null form as follows:

H₀₁: There is no significant positive effect of supervisor evaluation method of performance appraisal on job performance among non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka.

H₀₂: There is no significant positive impact of 360-Degree feedback method of performance appraisal on job performance among non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka.

H₀₃: There is no significant positive influence of rating scale method of performance appraisal on job performance among non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Performance Appraisal

Employee performance is evaluated and assessed as part of a performance evaluation process that helps with goal-setting, career growth, and identification of strengths and areas for improvement. In order to keep track of employee development, match personal objectives with business objectives, and assist in decision-making regarding promotions, pay increases, and other talent management programs, performance appraisals are usually carried out on a regular basis, such as annually or semi-annually (Farin, Akwari, Ededem & William, 2023). Organisations may access and manage employee performance, discover high-potential workers, offer development opportunities, reward and recognize exceptional performers with the aid of performance appraisals, which are crucial to talent management.

Organisations can make well-informed decisions on talent development, succession planning, and performance improvement plans by methodically analyzing employee performance (Kanisa & Makokha, 2017). Performance appraisal is an organized evaluation or assessment of employees work or contributions to the organisation (Kanisa & Makokha, 2017). Typically, this takes the shape of written submissions, online tests, and recurring interviews, among other formats (Armstrong, 2009). Organisations utilize assessments to find and recognize exceptional performance in the increasingly globalized environment. Firms use assessments, according to Wanjiku, (2018), to identify employee competence needs that call for capacity building or training in order to improve organisational performance.

Performance Appraisal Methods

Performance appraisal practices are crucial components of human resource management in universities, offering a structured way to assess employee performance and encourage professional growth. This section explores the different appraisal methods used in universities and examines how often and when appraisals occur in public compared to private institutions. Universities utilize a variety of performance

appraisal methods to assess the effectiveness of their non-academic staff. The most common methods include:

1. Self-Assessment Method

The traditional approach involves direct supervisors assessing the performance of their subordinates based on established criteria. Supervisor evaluations are often seen as more objective than self-assessments, as they offer an external viewpoint on employee performance (Ibrahim & Daniel, 2019).

2. Supervisor Evaluation Method

This traditional method involves direct supervisors evaluating the performance of their subordinates based on predetermined criteria. Supervisor evaluations are often regarded as more objective than self-assessments, as they provide an external perspective on employee performance (Ibrahim & Daniel, 2019).

3. 360-Degree Feedback Method

This thorough method gathers feedback from various stakeholders, including peers, subordinates, and supervisors. The 360-degree feedback approach provides a comprehensive view of an employee's performance and can highlight areas for improvement that might not be visible through other evaluation methods (Nutakor, 2019).

4. Rating Scales Method

Many universities utilize rating scales to measure performance across different dimensions such as job knowledge, teamwork, and communication skills. This approach offers a standardized way to compare employee performance but may sometimes oversimplify complex behaviors (Sagheer, 2024).

5. Competency-Based Appraisals

These evaluations focus on specific competencies necessary for a job role, assessing how effectively employees exhibit these competencies in their daily tasks. Competency-based evaluations align employee performance with organizational goals and expectations (Sulemana, 2013).

Employee Job Performance

Employee job performance is crucial to achieving organizational goals (Arubayi, Eromafuru, and Egbule 2020). As cited by Igbomor and Olisemenogor (2023) the effectiveness with which workers complete tasks that either directly support the organization's technological core by carrying out a portion of its technological process or indirectly by providing it with necessary materials or services is known as employee job performance. Employee job performance, according to Igbomor and Ogbuma (2024), is an assessment of a person's work-related abilities, knowledge, and results obtained at work. It involves evaluating an employee's ability to accomplish certain objectives, targets, and demands set by the organization as well as how well they carry out their assigned tasks and responsibilities.

Job performance can be defined as the extent to which an employee fulfils their job duties and responsibilities, contributing to the organization's overall goals (Adejare, Olaore, Udofia & Emola, 2020; Inayat & Khan, 2021). For non-academic staff in universities, job performance encompasses various tasks, including administrative support, financial management, student services, and facilities management. Metrics for evaluating job performance typically include both qualitative and quantitative measures:

Task Completion: This metric assesses how effectively employees complete assigned tasks within specified deadlines, focusing on both efficiency and effectiveness in executing responsibilities (Ibrahim & Daniel, 2019).

Quality of Work: The quality of output is critical for performance evaluation, encompassing accuracy, attention to detail, and compliance with institutional standards (Adejare et al., 2020).

Attendance and Punctuality: Regular attendance and punctuality are fundamental indicators of commitment to one's role (Dompelage, Gunawardhana, Kalansooriya & Peiris, 2019; (Nutakor, 2022)).

Factors Influencing Employee Job Performance within Higher Education Contexts

Several factors impact job performance among non-academic staff in higher education institutions. Understanding these factors is crucial for developing effective performance management strategies.

Job Satisfaction: Research shows that job satisfaction significantly influences employee performance. Non-academic staffs who are content with their roles tend to demonstrate higher productivity and commitment (Inayat & Khan, 2021).

Training and Development: Ongoing professional development is essential for enhancing employee skills and competencies. Adejare et al. (2020) emphasized that effective training programmes lead to improved service delivery among non-academic staff. Institutions that invest in training cultivate a more competent workforce capable of addressing organizational challenges.

Work Environment: The physical and psychological aspects of the work environment can significantly impact job performance. A supportive culture that encourages collaboration and open communication leads to better performance outcomes (Ibrahim & Daniel, 2019). Conversely, a negative work environment can result in decreased motivation and higher turnover rates.

Performance Appraisal Systems: The design and implementation of performance appraisal systems are also critical in influencing job performance. Fair and constructive appraisal processes can motivate employees to enhance their performance by providing clear feedback on their strengths and areas needing improvement (Nutakor, 2022). In summary, understanding the definition of job performance, the metrics for assessing it, and the various influencing factors is essential for enhancing the effectiveness of non-academic staff in both public and private universities.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a survey research design to examine the relationship between performance appraisals and employee job performance among non-academic staff at Delta State University, Abraka. The choice of this design made it possible for the researcher to collect relevant data through a self-administered questionnaire. The population of the study consisted of all non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka, totaling 1,767 employees, made up of 802 junior staff and 965 senior staff, as recorded by the institution's Human Resource Department in 2024. From this population, a sample size of 353 was determined using Yamane's formula at a 5% significance level. Bowley's proportion technique was then employed to allocate the sample proportionately between junior staff (160) and senior staff (193).

Data collection was carried out using a structured questionnaire, which contained two sections. Section A focused on the demographic characteristics of respondents, while Section B elicited information on their opinions concerning performance appraisal and job performance. To ensure clarity, the questionnaire was explained to respondents before administration.

Validity of the instrument was established through face and content validation. The questionnaire was reviewed by the research supervisor, who provided constructive feedback and modifications before it was administered. Reliability was confirmed using the Cronbach alpha test, which produced coefficients of 0.78 for supervisor evaluation, 0.74 for 360-degree feedback, 0.79 for the rating scale method, and 0.86 for employee job performance, indicating strong internal consistency.

The researcher, with the assistance of research assistants, personally distributed the questionnaires to respondents after providing a clear explanation of the study's objectives. Data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Pearson correlation was applied to establish the relationship between performance appraisal methods and job performance, while multiple regression analysis was used to determine the predictive impact of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Response Rate

The researcher administered three hundred and fifty three (353) copies of questionnaire to respondent out of which three hundred and thirty four (334) were complete and valid. However, 19 copies of the questionnaire were not returned. This information is presented in Table 4.1 below.

Table 4.1: Response rate

Response	Frequency
Copies of questionnaire distributed	353(100%)
Copies of questionnaire not returned	19(5%)
Copies of questionnaire returned and valid	334(95%)
Response rate	96%

Source: Author's Computation 2025

4.2 Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

In terms of gender distribution as shown in Table 4.2, there were 174 male respondents (52%) and 160 female respondents (48%), indicating a slight majority of males. Regarding age, 5.3% , 16.1% 32%, 40.4% and 6.25 fell within the age range of 18 – 25 years, 26–35 years, 36-45 years, 46-55 years and 56 years and above respectively. The educational qualifications reveal that most respondents hold HND/B.Sc degree 196 (58%), with 59(18%) having NCE/OND, 77(23%) possessing PGDE/MBA/M.Sc. and 2(1%) holding a Ph.D indicating a well-educated group.

Table 4.2: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Demographic Characteristics	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	174	52.0
	Female	160	48.0
	TOTAL	334	100.0
Age	18 – 25 years	18	5.3.
	26–35 years	54	16.1
	36-45 years	106	32.0
	46-55 years	135	40.4
	56 years and above	21	6.2
	TOTAL	334	100.0
Educational Qualifications	NCE/OND	59	18.0
	HND/B.Sc.	196	58.0
	PGDE/MBA/M.Sc.	77	23.0
	Ph.D.	2	1.0
	TOTAL	334	100.0

Source: Author's Computation 2025

4.3 Descriptive Statistic

Table 4.3 showed that all the variables exceeded the mean benchmark of 2.50 with respect to the independent variable (performance appraisal as determined by supervisor evaluation method, 360-Degree Feedback Method, Rating Scale Method), and the dependent variable (employee job performance). The mean score values clearly indicates that the respondents considered the instrument scales were useful for evaluating the relationship between employee work performance and performance appraisals. Additionally, as indicated by the standard deviation values, all variables displayed minimal variations in the data series, suggesting that respondents' perceptions of the topic are not widely separated from one another. Furthermore, the lowest and maximum scores fall between 1 and 4, indicating that the research instrument used in this study has a 4-point Likert scale.

Table 4.3 Descriptive Statistic

Variable	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Supervisor Evaluation Method	1	4	3.66	0.05
360-Degree Feedback Method	1	4	3.83	0.37
Rating Scale Method	1	4	3.63	0.55
Employee Job Performance	1	4	3.70	0.46

Source: Author's Computation 2025

4.4 Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

The VIF for each of the independent variables' dimensions is shown in Table 4.4. A statistical test called the Variance Inflation Factor is typically used to ascertain whether there is a strong correlation between the independent variable pairs. According to the VIF test results, the average VIF is 1.79, which is lower than the 10.0 standardized mean VIF. This demonstrates clearly that the dimensions of the independent variables employed in the study do not exhibit multicollinearity.

Table 4.4: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
Supervisor Evaluation Method	1.87	0.652
360-Degree Feedback Method	1.97	0.540
Rating Scale Method	1.54	0.608
Average VIF	1.79	

Source: Author's Computation 2025

4.5 Correlation Matrix

Presented in Table 4.5, is the Pearson correlation matrix employed to ascertain the relationship between the various method of performance appraisal and employee job performance. The result showed that there is a significant positive linkage between the various method of performance appraisal and employee job performance. The implication is that when supervisor evaluation, 360-Degree feedback, and rating scale method of performance appraisals is used to assess employee performance, it can lead to improved employee job performance.

Table 4.5: Correlation Matrix

		SEM	3DFM	RSM	EJP
SEM	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	1			
	N	334			
3DFM	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.362** 0.000	1		
	N	334	334		
RSM	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.563** 0.000	0.340** 0.000	1	
	N	334	334	334	
EJP	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.429** 0.000	0.321** 0.000	0.524** 0.000	1
	N	334	334	334	334

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Author's Computation, 2025

Key: ejp = employee job performance, sem= supervisor evaluation method, 3dfm= 360-Degree feedback method, rsm= rating scale method

4.6 Test of Hypotheses

Multiple Regression Analysis was used in this study to assess the hypotheses at the 5% significant level. The p-value determines whether or not we accept a hypothesis. If the p-value is >0.05 (more than 5%), we fail to reject the null hypothesis, meaning we accept it. If the p-value is <0.05 (less than 5%), we reject the null hypothesis.

The regression analysis showed the effect of performance appraisals on employee job performance in Table 4.6. The regression parameter for supervisor evaluation method (SEM) is 0.181 with a statistically significant t-statistic of 2.22, standard error of 0.082 and a corresponding p-value of 0.028. This indicates that there is a positive significant effect of SEM on employee job performance. This denotes that utilizing SEM of performance appraisal is associated with enhanced employee job performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

The regression parameter for 360-Degree feedback method (3DFM) is 0.219 and a standard error of 0.106, with a t-statistic of 2.07 which is positively and statistically significant at (p-value = 0.040). What this implies is that there is a significant and positive effect of 3DFM on employee job performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted.

Finally, rating scale method (RSM) showed a positive and substantial parameter of 0.321, standard error of 0.061 with a highly significant t-statistic (5.230) and a p-value (0.000). This indicates a strong effect of RSM on employee job performance. This denotes that utilizing RSM of performance appraisal is associated with enhanced job performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Table 4.6: Coefficient

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		Beta	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	4.630	2.846		1.627	.000
	SEM	0.181	0.082	0.161	2.216	0.028
	3DFM	0.219	0.106	0.129	2.065	0.040
	RSM	0.321	0.061	0.384	5.230	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Job Performance

Source: Author's Computation, 2025

Key: sem= supervisor evaluation method, 3dfm= 360-Degree feedback method, rsm= rating scale method

Table 4.7 presents the model summary. The value of R² which is 0.315 indicates that the independent variable (Supervisor evaluation method, 360-Degree feedback method, Rating scale method) explains only 31.5% systematic variation in employee job performance of non-academic staff in Delta State Universities, Abraka, Nigeria. In addition, the adjusted R-squared value of 0.302 indicates goodness of fit. This means that the overall model is significant as the independent variables were able to predict the dependent variable.

Table 4.7: Model Summary

Model	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.315	0.302	1.34920

a. Predictors: (Constant), Supervisor Evaluation method, 360-Degree feedback method, Rating scale method

Source: Author's Computation, 2025

At 0.000, the F statistic of 25.494 is significant as presented in Table 4.8. This indicates that there is a statistically significant relationship between performance appraisal methods and employee job performance among non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka.

Table 4.8: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	174.479	1	43.620	23.963	0.000 ^b
	Residual	378.629	334	1.820		
	Total	553.108	333			
A. Dependent Variable: Employee Job Performance						
B. Predictors: (Constant), Supervisor Evaluation method, 360-Degree feedback method, Rating scale method						

Source: Author's Computation, 2025

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study investigated the relationship between performance appraisal and employee job performance of non-academic staff in Delta State Universities, Abraka, Nigeria. The data that were obtained from the study respondents were analyzed and the result provided three key insights: first, there is a significant positive relationship between supervisor evaluation method of performance appraisal and job performance (p-value $0.028 < 0.05$). In other word, a supervisor evaluation method of performance appraisal has a positive and significant effect on employee job performance. This implies that supervisor evaluation which involves a process by which manager or supervisor assesses an employee's performance through direct observations and interactions enhance employee job performance. This evaluation uses a structured system to measure the employee's work against set criteria, with the supervisor serving as the main source of information for the performance review. This finding is supported by the finding of Wanjiru and Odenyo (2024) who found that supervisor evaluation methods of performance appraisal had positive and significant relationship with employee performance.

Secondly, a positive significant relationship was found on the association between 360-Degree feedback method of performance appraisal and employee job performance (p-value $0.040 < 0.05$). This indicates that 360-Degree feedback method of performance appraisal has a positive and significant effect on employee job performance. The implication is that the 360-degree feedback method of performance appraisal that involves collecting feedback on an employee's performance from various sources, such as their manager, peers, subordinates, and sometimes even external customers improves employee job performance. This approach provides a well-rounded perspective on their strengths and weaknesses by gathering insights from all directions. Consequently, the "360-degree feedback" is often utilized for developmental purposes, helping to pinpoint areas for improvement and enhance leadership skills. This finding is in line with the finding of Aturu-Aghedo (2023), Ezekiel (2022), Ohwona et al. (2023), Dike et al. (2021) and Ijeuru et al. (2024) who found in their studies that 360-Degree feedback method of performance appraisal has a positive and significant effect on employee job performance.

Thirdly, the result of this study also revealed that rating scale method of performance appraisal has a positive relationship/effect on employee job performance (p-value $0.000 < 0.05$). The rating scale method in performance appraisal is a system that evaluates an employee's performance against a set of predefined criteria. It uses a numbered scale to indicate their level of proficiency in each area, allowing for a quantitative assessment of their overall performance. Essentially, this method offers a structured way to rate an employee based on different aspects of their job through a numerical ranking system. This result is consistent with the finding of Aturu-Aghedo (2023) who found that employee performance is positively and significantly impacted by rating scales used in performance appraisals.

Overall, the finding of this study showed the performance appraisal has a substantial positive effect on employee job performance of non-academic staff in Delta State University, Abraka. Employees are able to identify their strength as well as their weakness through the assessment of their performance.

5.2 CONCLUSION

This study examined effect of performance appraisal on employee job performance of non-academic staff in Delta state Universities, Abraka, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to ascertain the effect of performance appraisal (supervisor evaluation method, 360-Degree feedback method and rating scale method) on employee job performance of non-academic staff in Delta State Universities, Abraka, Nigeria. The study concluded, based on the finding that performance appraisal (supervisor evaluation method, 360-Degree feedback method and rating scale method) has significant positive effect on employee job performance of non-academic staff in Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

The study makes the following recommendations:

1. Institutions should develop comprehensive performance appraisal systems that incorporate supervisor evaluations, consistent feedback, and effective rating scales to improve employee performance.
2. Training should be provided for individuals involved in the appraisal process. Equipping supervisors and managers with the necessary skills will enhance the quality of feedback delivered to non-academic staff.
3. Performance appraisal methods should be reviewed regularly to ensure their continued relevance and effectiveness.
4. The review process should include collecting feedback from staff about the appraisal system and making appropriate adjustments based on their input.
5. High-performing staff should be recognized and rewarded as a strategy to motivate others toward improved job performance.

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